

1 **Table S1.** Number of records per taxonomic category

Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
Annelida	1	15	43	186	336
Arthropoda	2	11	122	323	523
Bryozoa	2	3	47	81	141
Cnidaria	2	9	66	132	233
Echinodermata	4	21	40	68	74
Mollusca	5	52	190	466	939
Porifera	1	19	50	66	104
Total	17	130	558	1322	2350

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36 **Table S2.** Functional description and ecosystem relevance of each character used to
 37 estimate FD facets across the SEPC.

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Functional category	Functional importance	Traits	Description	Code
Tiering	Is the relationship of the organism with the substrate and the water column. Tiering level reflects the distribution of the food resources at micro-habitat level. Additionally, provides information regarding oxygenation and bioturbation levels, which makes it a good bioindicator of possible disturbance in the ecosystem. (Walker y Bambach 1974; Bambach et al. 2007; Bush et al. 2007).	Pelagic	Organisms that inhabit the water column (e.g., jellyfish). They play the role of incorporating organic carbon from the ocean surface through the pelagic zone (Henehan et al. 2016).	1
		Erect	Organisms with vertical growth towards the water column (e.g., corals). The erect characteristic favours the capture of food by filtration and prevents the burial of the organism by sedimentation by maintaining the flow of energy (Schack et al. 2020).	2
		Surficial	Organisms living on the substrate (e.g., limpets). The occurrence of this feature implies a high energy flux and remineralisation over the benthic and/or intertidal surface (Bambach et al. 2007; Belley & Snelgrove 2016).	3
		Infaunal	Organisms that live buried in the substrate (e.g., polychaetes). Bioturbating organisms modify biogeochemical processes and habitat structure (Queirós et al. 2013).	4
Motility Level	Indicates the possibility of an organism's ability to dispersal. Motility levels indicates the spatial extension of	Freely, Fast	Active, unrestricted movement (adherence). Rapid movement indicates active resource gathering and a wide	1

	activity ranges of the species. In addition, provide indirect information regarding physical interaction with other species, potential escape-response to any threat, high metabolic energy and need to be compensated by a higher energy input (Albouy et al. 2019).		spatial range (e.g., predatory crustaceans).	
		Freely, Slow	Active movement with strong adherence to the substrate. Slow movement suggests active resource gathering over a short spatial range (e.g., grazing echinoids).	2
		Faculty Unattached	Movement only, when necessary, no adherence to the substrate. Passive resource gathering, spatial range of activity expands upon disturbance (e.g., clams filter feeders).	3
		Faculty Attached	Movement only when necessary, organism attached to the substrate. Passive collection of resources, the spatial range of activity is extended by a disturbance) e.g. mussel filter feeders).	4
		Non-Motile Unattached	Movement only when necessary, organism attached to substrate. Passive resource gathering, spatial range of activity expands upon disturbance (e.g., clams filter feeders). (e.g. scallops).	5
		Non-Motile Attached	No movement, attached to the substrate. Passive resource gathering, spatial range of activity is limited to the position of the organism (e.g., filter-feeding bryozoans).	6
Feeding Mechanisms	Feeding mechanisms reflects the energy flow and biomass between across trophic levels on the ecosystem. Alternatively, reflects type and quantity of resources available, and provides a relative	Suspension	Organisms that capture food particles from water by filtration. Primary consumers in the food web, they are essential intermediaries in the energy flow establishing the link between primary production and	1

	measure of interaction between species. (Henriquez et al. 2017, Schumm et al. 2019).		consumers (Wang et al. 2015).	
		Surface Deposit	Organisms that capture accumulated loose particles from a substrate. Depositivores drive the recirculation of accumulated particles in the substrate as they are consumed by predators (Shull 2019).	2
		Grazing	Organisms that scrape or graze algae on the substrate. They incorporate the energy transformed by primary algal productivity into the system (Smetacek et al. 2004).	3
		Predatory	Organisms that actively capture prey. Predation has a direct effect on the density of primary consumers, and an indirect effect on primary production (O'Connor & Bruno 2007).	4
		Omnivore	Organisms that obtain food from a variety of sources. supplementary feeding of omnivores attenuates the cascading effect in a food web in the face of potential disturbances (Eriksson et al. 2011).	5
		Chemotrophic	Organisms that perform chemo-symbiotic or chemical synthesis. This strategy incorporates energy directly into the system. Driven by intense solar radiation coupled with interaction between symbiotic species (Bellwood et al. 2018).	6
Life Forms	Life type indicates whether organisms exhibit inter- or intraspecific	Colonial	Organisms that create cooperative, interconnected groups, reducing intraspecific	1

	associations in response to ecological and/or environmental constraints (Navarro et al. 2020; Schack et al. 2020).		competition. This trait maximises resource extraction by filtration (e.g., sponges), distributing energy among all individuals in the colony (Schack et al. 2020)	
		Solitary	Non-cooperative, often mobile, individual organisms. Symbiotic relationship with another species. Symbiosis favors the obtaining of resources and the joint survival of the species involved (e.g., corals-zooxanthellae) (Navarro et al. 2020).	2
		Symbiont	Non-cooperative, often mobile, individual organisms. Symbiotic relationship with another species. Symbiosis favours the obtaining of resources and the joint survival of the species involved (e.g. corals-zooxanthellae) (Navarro et al. 2020).	3
Type of Reproduction	Reproductive type is determined by the number of reproductive events of an organism over its life cycle (Hughes 2017). Reproductive events are related to metabolic rates and the amount of energy flowing through the system (Moorcroft 2009; Wangenstein et al. 2016).	Semelparity	A single reproductive event in its entire life cycle. Semiparity is selected in organisms with slow developmental rates that invest all their energy in the reproductive event, with the aim of reducing intraspecific competition between population cohorts, increasing fitness, and increasing the survival of juvenile organisms (Bradshaw and McMahon, 2008).	1
		Iteroparity	Several reproductive events throughout the life cycle. Iteroparity reflects ecosystems with a constant incorporation of	2

			energy into the system, due to the high metabolic expenditure involved in the periodic release of fertilised eggs (Wangensteen et al. 2016).	
Type of Larval	The early developmental stages of marine invertebrates influence the length of the life span in the water column of larvae and therefore the dispersal ability of the species (Hickman et al. 2001, Brown et al. 2018).	Planktotrophic	Larval stage that feeds on plankton. This type of larva demands high nutrient incorporation into the water column, favouring an increase in the duration of the larval stage and dispersal potential (Fernandez et al. 2009).	1
		Lecithotrophic	Larval stages with a yolk reserve. This strategy reduces larval time in the water column, which reduces predation pressure in the pelagic phase (Brown et al. 2018).	2
		Direct Development	No larval stage (juvenile equals adult). The absence of the larval stage increases survival and direct incorporation of "ecologically fit" juveniles to compete and colonise available habitat.	3
Survival Strategy	Strategies developed to resist or avoid predation. Ecosystems with high energy assimilation through food webs exhibit higher metabolic cost traits (e.g., development of toxins and mechanical structures) (Pawlik 2012; Franklin et al. 2020).	Escape/Hold on	Predator flight or substrate attachment system. These strategies indicate low energy consumption compared to the development of toxins or structures (Pawlik 2012).	1
		Fight	It is related to the territorial behaviour of some organisms and involves less energy consumption and the development of toxins (Pawlik 2012).	2
		Chelminical/Mechanic	Development of mechanical structures	3

			(e.g., spines) or toxins (e.g. stinging cells). Those strategies are characteristic of high energy demand.	
Body Side	Size range reflects the position in food webs and metabolic ranges of organisms, with larger sizes suggesting slower development of organisms associated with lower metabolic rates (Henriquez et al. 2017; Floyd et al. 2020). On the other hand, size indicates the fraction of biomass that is transformed in the ecosystem and is a fundamental trait that provides information about the contribution of species in the production, transformation, and incorporation of energy into the ecosystem (Ramírez-Ortiz et al. 2017).	<10 mm	Small size	1
		10 To 50 mm	Medium small size	2
		50 To 100 mm	Medium large size	3
		>100 mm	Large size	4

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49 **Table S3.** Relationship between species richness and number of FEs assigned to each
 50 biogeographical region: (df) degrees of freedom, (*n*) numerator, (*d*) denominator, (F) F
 51 value, (*a*) intercept, (*b*) slope, (*r*²): significance levels (*p*< 0.001=**, *p*< 0.0001=***).

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FD	Biogeographic region	df_{<i>n,d</i>}	F	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>r</i>²
FE	Tropical	1, 13	51.05	1.42 ± 0.07	0.17 ± 0.02	0.82***
	Warm-Temperate	1, 34	1900	0.53 ± 0.03	0.57 ± 0.01	0.98***
	Cold-Temperate	1, 14	11.43	1.25 ± 0.17	0.21 ± 0.06	0.53**

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82 **Table S4.** Data provided by the similarity percentage test (SIMPER) comparing the
83 functional structure of three biogeographic units of the South American Pacific. They result
84 in a mean of Bray-Curtis dissimilarity = 29% in the relative abundances of 31 functional
85 traits among tropic warm and cold.

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Functional Traits	Relative Abundance Mean			Dissimilarity Mean	Percentage Contribution
	Tropic	Warm	Cold		
Chemotrophic	0.049	0.007	0.012	2.071	7.271
Faculty Attached	0.041	0.011	0.008	1.584	5.559
Direct Development	0.003	0.015	0.031	1.464	5.141
Symbiont	0.038	0.012	0.009	1.402	4.920
Semelparity	0.008	0.013	0.031	1.316	4.619
Non-Motile Unattached	0.004	0.016	0.027	1.264	4.437
Lecithotrophic	0.014	0.012	0.030	1.251	4.391
Freely Slow	0.033	0.011	0.016	1.239	4.349
Faculty Unattached	0.004	0.017	0.026	1.195	4.197
<10mm	0.020	0.011	0.026	1.148	4.030
Pelagic	0.031	0.014	0.011	1.004	3.525
Colonial	0.020	0.012	0.025	0.987	3.464
Suspension	0.022	0.012	0.023	0.951	3.337
Erect	0.018	0.013	0.024	0.840	2.949
Chemical/Mechanic	0.026	0.013	0.018	0.826	2.899
Surficial	0.027	0.013	0.016	0.825	2.895
Fight	0.009	0.016	0.023	0.810	2.845
Planktotrophic	0.026	0.013	0.016	0.732	2.570
Non-Motile Attached	0.018	0.013	0.023	0.727	2.551
Surface Deposit	0.022	0.014	0.017	0.712	2.500
10 to 50mm	0.025	0.014	0.016	0.675	2.370
Iteroparity	0.024	0.014	0.017	0.655	2.301
Omnivore	0.023	0.013	0.019	0.629	2.208
Infaunal	0.011	0.017	0.019	0.628	2.203
Solitary	0.023	0.014	0.017	0.603	2.118
Predatory	0.024	0.014	0.016	0.598	2.098
Escape/Hold on	0.022	0.014	0.018	0.589	2.067
50 to 100mm	0.021	0.015	0.017	0.503	1.765
>100mm	0.021	0.015	0.017	0.446	1.567
Freely Fast	0.022	0.015	0.015	0.443	1.556
Grazing	0.019	0.015	0.017	0.370	1.300

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89 **Table S5.** ANOVA of key factors in the canonical correspondence analysis (CCA) model
 90 performed to assess the significant of the final model (a), each term or trait (b) and each
 91 axis (c). Significant values: ***= $p \leq 0.0001$, **= $p \leq 0.001$, *= $p \leq 0.05$, n.s. = $p \geq 0.05$.

a) Final model

	Df	X²	F
Model	7	0.57255	21.973***
Residual	53	0.19729	

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b) by “terms” (environmental drivers)

Drivers	Df	X²	F
Latitude	1	0.33364	89.629***
SST	1	0.05902	15.8548***
O ₂	1	0.07848	21.0824***
Carbon	1	0.00441	1.1851 ^{n.s.}
Nitrate	1	0.02853	7.664***
Chlo	1	0.01035	2.7803***
Area	1	0.05812	15.6127***
Residual	53	0.19729	

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c) by “axis”

Axis	Df	X²	F
CCA1	1	0.35943	96.5572***
CCA2	1	0.12423	33.3732***
CCA3	1	0.06293	16.9045***
CCA4	1	0.01296	3.4829*
CCA5	1	0.00825	2.2151
CCA6	1	0.00292	0.7838
CCA7	1	0.00183	0.4916
Residual	53	0.19729	

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104 **Table S6.** ANOVA of key factors in the canonical correspondence analysis (CCA) model
 105 performed to assess the significant of the final model (a), each term or trait (b) and each
 106 axis (c). Significant values: ***= $p \leq 0.0001$, **= $p \leq 0.001$, *= $p \leq 0.05$, n.s. = $p \geq 0.05$.

a) Final model

	Df	X ²	F
Model	31	0.7462	29.536***
Residual	29	0.02363	

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b) by “terms” (traits)

	Df	X ²	F
Latitude	1	0.33364	409.3917***
Pelagic	1	0.06957	85.3713***
Benthic Erect	1	0.05891	72.291***
Benthic Surficial	1	0.10694	131.2213***
Infaunal	1	0.01688	20.7139***
Freely Fast	1	0.00854	10.4734***
Freely Slow	1	0.01084	13.3062***
Fac Unattached	1	0.01659	20.3596***
Fac Attached	1	0.01118	13.7203***
Non Motile Unattached	1	0.01561	19.1545***
Non Motile Attached	1	0.0125	15.3414***
Suspension	1	0.00252	3.0884*
Surface Deposit	1	0.01543	18.9294***
Grazing	1	0.00866	10.6223***
Predatory	1	0.00304	3.7275*
Omnivory	1	0.00409	5.0242**
Chemotrophic	1	0.00679	8.3279***
Colonial	1	0.00384	4.706**
Solitary	1	0.0046	5.6494***
Symbiont	1	0.00217	2.6598*
Semelparity	1	0.00659	8.0909***
Planktotrophic	1	0.00283	3.4728*
Lecithotrophic	1	0.00113	1.3919*
Direct Develoment	1	0.00221	2.7108*
Escape Hold on	1	0.00399	4.9019**
Fight	1	0.00208	2.5473*
Chelminical Mechanic	1	0.00283	3.4701**
<Size 0.10mm	1	0.00388	4.7589**

Size 10 to 50mm	1	0.00324	3.9815*
Size 50 to 100mm	1	0.00238	2.921*
>Size 100mm	1	0.00269	3.2965*
Residual	29	0.02363	

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c) by “axis”

	Df	χ^2	F
CCA1	1	0.36729	450.6832***
CCA2	1	0.12744	156.3736***
CCA3	1	0.06984	85.696***
CCA4	1	0.03757	46.1028***
CCA5	1	0.02816	34.5531***
CCA6	1	0.02162	26.5246***
CCA7	1	0.02	24.5373***
CCA8	1	0.01226	15.0388***
CCA9	1	0.01132	13.8868***
CCA10	1	0.01009	12.3859***
CCA11	1	0.00804	9.8652***
CCA12	1	0.00723	8.8671***
CCA13	1	0.00571	7.0031**
CCA14	1	0.00496	6.0812**
CCA15	1	0.00299	3.6743
CCA16	1	0.00215	2.6369
CCA17	1	0.00197	2.4134
CCA18	1	0.00141	1.7335
CCA19	1	0.00111	1.3648
CCA20	1	0.00092	1.1228
CCA21	1	0.0009	1.1052
CCA22	1	0.00074	0.9092
CCA23	1	0.00051	0.6293
CCA24	1	0.0005	0.6168
CCA25	1	0.00042	0.5116
CCA26	1	0.0003	0.3636
CCA27	1	0.00022	0.2649
CCA28	1	0.00019	0.2348
CCA29	1	0.00018	0.2264
CCA30	1	0.0001	0.1252
CCA31	1	0.00007	0.0913
Residual	29	0.02363	

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110 **Table S7.** Conditional importance of the ranges of environmental variability, obtained from
 111 the random forest model. VIF: Variance inflation factor to identify collinearity among
 112 predictors. NSp: Species richness. RaoQ: Rao's quadratic entropy. FRic: Functional
 113 richness. FRed: Functional redundancy. FEve: Functional evenness. FSpe: Functional
 114 specialization. Significance levels for each predictor ($p < 0.05 = *$, $p < 0.01 = **$, $p <$
 115 $0.001 = ***$), n.s.: no significant effect.

Variables	VIF	NSp	RaoQ	FRic	FRed	FEve	FSpe
SST [°C]	1.0	100***	31.958**	62.71***	64.17***	100***	37.90***
Chl [mg/m ³ ×day ⁻¹]	4.8	46.99**	25.6*	27.16*	28.52*	72.15***	28.25*
Carbon [g/m ³ ×day ⁻¹]	4.7	27.60 ^{n.s.}	100***	100***	100***	22.84 ^{n.s.}	100***

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